

Table: Challenges of applying process mining

Category	Challenge	Reference
Knowledge	Knowledge sharing	[1]
	Unwillingness to share domain knowledge	[2]
	Technical capabilities of the staff	[6]
	Inconsistent usage of different mining tools	[8]
Data protection	Understanding the logged information	[5]
	Restricting data privacy regulations	[2]
	Rating employees based on process mining	[2], [10], [7]
	General privacy issues	[4]
Availability of event logs	Data access barriers	[2]
	Unavailability of data	[2]
	Scattered event data	[1]
	Inconsistency in data	[8]
Process structure	Difficulties in analyzing multiple processes	[6]
	Difficulties with complex processes	[5]
Software	Difficulties in software selection	[1]
	Missing advanced features in PM software	[2]
	Non-standard visualization techniques	[2]
	Too few usages of declarative models	[2]
	Technical challenges regarding a software	[6]
	Lack of user-tailoredness	[6]
	Missing benchmarks for mining software	[3]
	Missing added value	[2], [4]
Management Support	Unclear organizational anchoring	[2]
	Issues with governance structures	[6]
	Continuous incorporation as a problem	[2], [4]
	Resistance to change behavior	[2]
	Lack of a process mining methodology	[9], [3]
Methodology	Creation of a suitable event data set	[10], [4], [7]
	Collecting event data for process mining	[5]
Data collection	Lack of trust in process mining insights	[2]
Perceived benefits	Exaggerated expectations on PM	[2]
Inclusion of stakeholders	Lack of interdisciplinary teams	[2]
	Conflicts between experts and users	[6]
Data quality	Poor data quality	[2]
	Complex data preparation	[2]
	Insufficient data orientation	[2]
	Data redundancies	[6], [5]
	Inconsistent naming conventions	[6]
	Unstructured event log	[3]
	Process Changes	[5]
	Incorrect logging	[5]
	Difficulties in algorithm selection	[3], [9]
	Real-time system integration	[2]
Miscellaneous	Unclear success factors	[2]
	Missing implementation guidelines	[2]
	Aversion to transparency	[2]
	Difficult analysis of process exceptions	[2]
	Clarity of the problem formulation	[9]
	Inconsistency in meaning	[8]
	Fragmented solutions	[2]
	IT infrastructure	[10]

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